

The Relationship of Marxism and Literary Theories with the Common Grounds of Phenomenology

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Abstract

The ground aspects of phenomenological perspective provide a wide range of the literature study in collaboration with literary theories but the same, the Marxism cannot be studied better in the phenomenological perspectives rather it can be better studied in critical perspectives. The relationship of the Marxism and literary theories with phenomenological common grounds is highlighted in the current study through descriptive method of research. The study illustrates the relationship of Marxism and literary theories in phenomenological perspectives in the light of previous studies and as a sample textual analysis of Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*.

Keywords: Phenomenology, Marxism, Literary Theories

1. Introduction

Critical theory in literature is a specific approach in which deals with the social sciences and the power of special analysis with respect to politics, economy, dominance exploit and ideology. It is based on the judgment that dominates the problem which is needed to be explored dominantly in society. The question is raised that how does political communication affect the opinion and practices in the society. The modern political issues can be manipulated by literary theory. Karl Marx and his Marxian tradition help to understand the categorical needs of society because Marxian theory helps to understand critical question of power, dominance, exploitation and struggle of demand in the society. Marxian inspired, traditionally employ the term "critical" to describe that all sciences not only critical but has administrative character that take power structure for granted, but does not help to understand the meaning of legitimating.

Phenomenology is an approach develops by Edmund Husserl which is based on the human experience and the way the things are perceived and area to the human senses. It has become the new critical approach for evaluating the literature and literary aspects in context to ground realities. Qutoshi (20118) says that phenomenology has become a new phenomenon and theoretical guidelines for the researchers that help to understand the phenomenon at the subject level of the reality. Creswell (2017) says that phenomenology is descriptive in its nature which provides the wider meaning of living experiences to study the things under consciousness. Fotchman (2008) illustrates that the roots of phenomenology are found in the writings of Plato, Socrates and Aristotle as the philosophy of human beings.

Marxism was developed to establish a brand-new economic and political order wherein the powers that be manipulate the rights of the countries. This theory describes the relationship between the social stakeholder groups in terms of power issues based on wealth and the distribution of power. The theory was initially used for political purposes, but later it was recognised as a theory of literary criticism. In their book "The Communist Manifesto," Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels introduced the idea of an ethics of values. The socioeconomic and ideological underpinnings of his book gave priority to the social creation of society's values and socioeconomic system. Marx's book's concept of morals and ethics was dubbed Marxism in the historical period during which the theory of Marxism was created. The foundational principles of ethics and life values have been impacted by this philosophy. According to Eagleton (1996), Marxism is a broad spectrum of theoretical analysis that aids in understanding the ideologies, concepts, values, and experiences that a society went through at the time. The literary theory of feminism, which Marxism challenges and confronts power politics in the framework of masculine and dominating thinking of the systems of the society, is examined in opposition to Marxism, it is also noted.

As Marxism helps in the manipulation of society's hidden powers, this idea has emerged as a master pioneer of theoretical analysis in the investigation of how class and value competition is managed. The problem arises when the relationship between social classes and life's realities are discussed because people are then forced to view the things as the power, being carried up in the social hierarchy. On the other hand, philosophy offers the foundation for analyzing the realities as they are presented in society. The relationship between literary ideas and Marxism and the everyday realities of life will also be covered in the current study.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Literature is being studied now days under the perspectives of only literary theories but through these literary theories the ground realities of the time are being neglected which provides the basis to more understand the pieces of writings.

1.2. Significance of the Study

The currents study is unique in its nature which will provide a model to understand the relationship of Marxism and literary theories with the ground realities of phenomenology.

1.3. Objectives

- To compare literary theories with philosophy.

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- To manipulate the relationship of Marxism and literary theories with the common grounds of phenomenology.

1.4. Limitation of the Study

The current study is limited to the exposition of the ground aspects of phenomenology, literary theories and Marxism relationship. In the present study, the two pieces of texts are being analyzed to support the relationships of the theories, Marxism and phenomenology.

2. Literature Review

Emami (2011) conducted a research study on “*An Anti-social Socialist: A Critical Reading of Arthur Miller ‘s Death of Salesman*” in which it was described that Miller tried his best to illustrate the social factors being have no influence on the characters of the society. It is also described in the study that Marxism’s effect is not being shown in the novel as the capitalism put the impacts and values on the social life. It is concluded in the study that the role of woman in the novel is limited to as the persuasion of the things rather than discrimination. The society is being depicted in respect to describe the social influence on the characters rather than the impact of Marxism on the lives.

Reddy& Visakhapatnam (2014) in his study “*A Critical Analysis of Marxism and Literature by Edmund Wilson*” illustrated that literature is being analyzed after the Marxism critical theory because the Marxism provides extensive system of social and economic systems. Being adopted as the literary theory it can address the social relationships of power and politics. In the study, further it is told that the intentions of the writers are to illustrate the things in artistic way and the writers of the literature must keep in concern that there is difference between literature and journalism as the journalism is full of power and political aspects rather the literature has to be least concern with the social and economic powers.

Qin (2013) investigated on “*Defending Husserlian Phenomenology from Terry Eagleton ‘s Critique*” in which he told about the basis of the phenomenology which illustrate the ground realities of the life where the Terry Eagleton ‘s Critique highlights the historical and radical basis through which the life and the realities of the life must be studied. The study also revealed that the historical perspectives are neglected in the phenomenological perspectives when the study of the things is done in the prescriptive way. It is also concluded that the reality based theory which is appropriate in study of the life is phenomenology.

Hamadi (2017) did a study on “*The Concept of Ideology in Marxist Literary Criticism*”. The development of Marxist literary theory in general and the idea of ideology in particular are explored in this article. The study focuses on major Marxist figures, examines their most notable works, and throws light on their contributions to the theory and the area of literary criticism in order to demonstrate the significant role this theory plays in the field of literary criticism. To achieve this, the paper begins with the fundamental Marxist reading principles established by Marx and Engels and then analyses the changes brought about by other critics, particularly Althusser, Jameson, and Eagleton in their attempts to highlight the significance of ideology in interpreting literature and comprehending its origins, purposes, and methods. The methodology, therefore include a historical overview, illuminating early Marxist viewpoints, contrasting and comparing the additions and modifications made by notable Marxist thinkers, and illustrating with examples of literary texts and how they are seen and analyzed by these Marxist scholars. The study came to the conclusion that even though there are many different ways that Marxist literary critics see the idea of ideology, they all share the belief that “ideas are weapons in a field of conflict.” In conclusion, it sounds correct to agree with Walter Kendrick that literature “is an ideological term, the more so because it professes not to be.” And all teachers of literature, whether they identify as Arnoldians or Deconstructionists, are Ideologues.

Bashir, Mir & Mehmood (2019) researched on “*Marxism and Literature: Marxist Analysis of ‘The Garden Party’*”. According to the study, Marxism primarily addresses a person’s social behaviour toward others, particularly those who belong to different social groups. Despite the fact that Marxism has been extensively researched in relation to literature, psychology, sociology, and other fields, there are still many literary genres that need to be examined from a Marxist perspective. Short stories frequently portray life in a realistic manner, necessitating a Marxist analysis. One such masterwork, Katherine Mansfield’s “The Garden Party,” which is full of themes and characters that everyone encounters on a regular basis in life, hasn’t yet been examined in light of any economic or social theory. The goal of the current study is to analyze this narrative using Marxist principles in order to uncover its many implications and to broaden the scope of this economic and political philosophy. This research method uses qualitative analysis of “words and phrases” to identify the main subject. The results of this study provide insight into the social state of the average person, highlighting the oppression of the lower social classes at the hands of the upper classes as well as the function of ideology in upholding the status quo. Additionally, it examines class politics to see how social class shapes individuals and influences their behaviour.

3. Research Methodology

The current study is descriptive and qualitative in its nature which is conducted to highlight the relationship of Marxism and literary theories in relation with the common grounds of phenomenology. Gay (2012) describes qualitative approach as the analysis of the issues in textual form in which the issues are discussed with respect to theories and ground realities.

3.1. Data Analysis Process

The current study is also descriptive in which the already conducted research studies of Marxism, literary theories and phenomenology will be discussed to make the manipulation of the relationship among them. In this part, two pieces of texts are also been taken to support the idea of the relationship of phenomenology, literary theories and Marxism.

4. Analysis and Discussion

4.1. Comparison of Philosophy and Critical Theories

Philosophy is the study in which the things are perceived on the basis of ground realities and the questioning is raised towards the universe. There have been three different subdivisions which illustrate the philosophy more clearly and answer the questions about nature, values and reality.

4.2. Common Grounds of Phenomenology and Literary Theories

Fuchs (2015) in his study "*Critical Theory*" illustrated the dimensions of the philosophy and its relations to critical theories. In philosophical aspects, he described the critical theories with six different dimensions of the philosophy and he also gave the names of six dimensions of the critical theories as well.

Fuchs tells that the early first dimensions of the critical theory is the epistemology and says that it deals with the theory of knowledge. Fuchs says that these concepts tell about the theory that where from these theories are being constituted and organized. The next dimension as the ontology that tells about the reality of the masses that how the reality is being organized and developed. The next third dimension is the praxeology that illustrates the study of actions especially the political and ethical. Fuchs illustrate other three dimensions as the parts of the mentioned dimensions as these illustrate the relationship of philosophy with the theory as the theory is the science of literature while the philosophy is the science of mind and soul. Fuchs describes the philosophical basis as the basis of theory, neglecting the historical aspects.

4.3. Relationship of Marxism and Literary Theory

In his study, Fuchs characterizes critical theory as the science that manipulates the conflicts in society and characters as they are depicted in literature. The socioeconomic and political linkages between the masses are also illustrated by Marxism, including those between subject and object, goods and money, no owners and owners, company and sector, gender and power, wealth and work. Marxism, on the other hand, is simply understood as the socioeconomic system in the past, although it also illustrates these features. It has provided solutions to the contradictions in society in recent studies.

Because the links between the objects are unbalanced in both the postcolonial theory and the Marxist theory, Sinha (2015) argues that the postcolonial theory has left less masses to be examined or criticized than the Marxist theory does.

In the contrast, it can also be observed that in the perspective of feminism, Marxism does not allow female gender to be powerful. The feminist theory suggests that the status of the women is not given equally in the society so the feminist theory cannot answer the things properly as the relationship of the things is being told by Marxism.

4.4. Textual Analysis

In the perspective of the relationship of Marxism, literary theories and phenomenological, the following text extracted from Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* can illustrate the relationship more clearly.

"It is a truth universally acknowledged that a single man in possession of a good fortune must be in want of a wife."

Jane Austen 'style of writing shows the ground realities of the society through which the social and feministic issues are being described. In the feministic perspectives, it can be observed that the female characters of the society of that time have no specific emotions to be fulfilled rather than their parents were concerned only to marry them. In Marxism perspectives, portray of the male characters are being shown as the symbolic of wealth and the people who have wealth must have a wife. In the Marxist perspectives, the male characters would have a wife because they have wealth. In the feministic perspectives, it can be said that the role of female is limited, given by the society so they are not given opportunity in selection of a husband even they have good fortune or not. The capital is far away from most of females then how it could be managed. In phenomenological perspectives, the marriage of female was the big problem at that time while the reality is being ignored as the power and wealth was in the part of the male members of the society. "For what do we live, but to make sport for our neighbors, and laugh at them in our turn?"

Marxists' socioeconomic theory explains how a society becomes unbalanced when its capital is concentrated in the hands of a small number of individuals, leading to unrest and imbalance among the rest of the population. According to Marxist viewpoints, the aforementioned lines demonstrate the influence of capital: when a person has more money, his or her attitude is slightly altered, and emotions of superiority are ingrained in their behaviour. Similar ideas are demonstrated when sociocultural theory and the real world are likewise overlooked as stated in the lines.

5. Conclusion

The relationship of literary theories with Marxism and phenomenological ground realities is very much of importance because by studying both jointly the clearer picture of the literature is shown. The study of literature through

perspective of literary theories help to understand the hidden theology of the writer but the literary theories in collaboration with Marxism, presents the more clear understanding of the texts. After discussion, it can be observed that literary theories can be studied in the phenomenological perspective but the study of Marxism, as the theory, cannot be well understood. It can also be seen that phenomenology does not study the historical perspectives of the things as the literary theories and the Marxism criticism describe.

5.1. Recommendations

- There is strong relationship of literary theories and Marxism, so by analyzing both as criticism, the literature can be best understood.
- Literary theories can be studied under phenomenological perspectives but the Marxism neglects the ground realities so the text must be studied through literary aspects.
- Phenomenology must be considered as the literary criticism as it advocates the ground realities of the time.
- Marxism is least concerned with ground realities and phenomenology so it is unable to describe the past perspectives in the study.
- For better understanding of texts, the text must be studied in two dimensions which is Marxism and literary theories, and literary theories and phenomenology.

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